

Synthesis of some new arylidenes-substituted phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-4-oxo-thiazolidines : Antimicrobial and diuretic activities

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Abstract : A series of new [2-(substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol}]4-oxo-thiazolidines, 3(a-o) have been synthesized via the condensation of 5-(substituted phenyl)-2-(2-substituted benzylidene amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, 2(a-o) with thioglycolic acid. The compounds 2(a-o) were synthesized from 5-(substituted phenyl)-2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole, 1(a-c) with various aromatic aldehydes which itself was prepared from substituted aromatic acid(s) using thiosemicarbazide. The compounds 3(a-o) on treatment with various aromatic aldehydes afforded [5-(substituted arylidenes)-2-(substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol}]4-oxo-thiazolidines, 4(a-o). The structures of all the synthesized compounds have been determined by spectral and chemical methods. The compounds 2, 3 and 4 were screened for their antifungal and antibacterial activities against *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium* and *B. subtilis* bacteria and *R. oryzae*, *C. albicans* and *A. niger* fungi and diuretic activity on adult male rats.

Keywords : New thiazolidines, antimicrobial, diuretic activity.

Introduction

1,3,4-Thiadiazoles and their derivatives have been reported to possess broad spectrum biological activities including antituberculosis¹, anticonvulsant, anti-inflammatory², insecticidal³, antifungal⁴ and herbicidal properties⁵. 4-Oxo-thiazolidines^{4,6} and their 5-arylidenes⁷ are also known to possess various biological activities. In view of the above mentioned facts we describe herein the synthesis of some new compounds having arylated thiazolo arylidines and evaluated for their antifungal, antibacterial and diuretic activities⁸⁻¹⁰.

The sequence of reactions leading to the formation of the desired products are obtained in the Scheme 1. The compounds 1(a-c) were synthesized by the reported method¹. The compounds 1(a-c) on reaction with various aldehydes afforded 5-(substituted phenyl)-2-(2-substituted benzylidene amino)-1,3,4-thiazolidines, 2(a-o). The compounds 2(a-o) on treatment with thioglycolic acid produced [2-(substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol}]4-oxo-thiazolidines, 3(a-o). The thiazolidinones, 3(a-o) on reaction again with various aldehydes yielded the final products [5-(substituted arylidenes)-2-(substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-

1,3,4-thiadiazol}]4-oxo-thiazolidines, 4(a-o). The characterization data of compounds are given in Table 1.

Biological activity :

Antimicrobial activity :

The compounds 2, 3 and 4 were screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium* and *B. subtilis* and antifungal activity against *R. oryzae*, *C. albicans* and *A. niger* by filter paper disc technique^{11,12}. Standard antibacterial streptomycin and antifungal griseofulvin were also screened under similar conditions for comparison. Results are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Diuretic activity :

Diuretic activity of the compounds 2, 3 and 4 were tested by Lipschitz method^{13,14} in adult male rats, fasted overnight with free access to water loaded orally with 5 mL/100 g bw normal saline. All the test compounds (50 g/kg oral) and standard drug furosemide (Lasix) at a dose of 30 mg/kg (oral), suspended in 0.5% gum acacia and administered to the animals of respective groups in a volume of 5 mL/100 g. One group of animals was taken as control. All animals were used once a week. The urine flow was in order of 1 mL/h/rat. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 1. Characterization data of the compounds 2(b-o), 3(b-o) and 4(b-o)

Compd.	Ar	Ar ¹	Ar ²	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	Found (Calcd.) % :		
							C	H	N
2b	C ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	115–116	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	57.98 (58.04)	3.13 (3.22)	18.00 (18.05)
2c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	162–164	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	64.84 (64.97)	4.87 (4.99)	14.16 (14.21)
2d	C ₆ H ₅	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	132–133	71	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SBr	52.39 (52.48)	2.59 (2.62)	12.18 (12.24)
2e	C ₆ H ₅	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	142–144	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	66.18 (66.23)	5.10 (5.19)	18.07 (18.18)
2f	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	—	168–169	87	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	52.01 (52.09)	2.55 (2.60)	16.17 (16.20)
2g	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	184–186	74	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄ S	50.62 (50.68)	2.47 (2.53)	19.64 (19.71)
2h	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	158–159	73	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	56.39 (56.45)	3.47 (3.52)	16.38 (16.46)
2i	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	114–116	86	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	46.22 (46.27)	2.28 (2.31)	14.32 (14.39)
2j	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	161–163	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S	57.72 (57.79)	4.19 (4.24)	19.78 (19.83)
2k	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	—	192–193	79	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂	53.78 (53.87)	2.51 (2.69)	12.53 (12.57)
2l	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	142–143	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ OSCl	52.15 (52.24)	2.57 (2.61)	16.19 (16.25)
2m	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	186–187	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ OSCl	58.18 (58.27)	3.61 (3.64)	12.62 (12.74)
2n	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	176–177	65	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SBrCl	47.51 (47.56)	2.31 (2.37)	12.01 (12.09)
2o	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	184–186	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl ₂	59.52 (59.56)	4.29 (4.37)	16.31 (16.35)
3b	C ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	160–161	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	53.00 (53.09)	3.07 (3.12)	14.46 (14.57)
3c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	151–152	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	58.45 (58.50)	4.00 (4.09)	11.30 (11.37)
3d	C ₆ H ₅	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	190–192	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ OS ₂ Br	48.71 (48.82)	2.79 (2.87)	9.95 (10.04)
3e	C ₆ H ₅	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	168–170	71	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS ₂	59.61 (59.65)	4.61 (4.70)	14.58 (14.65)
3f	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	—	172–174	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	48.68 (48.72)	2.59 (2.62)	13.31 (13.37)
3g	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	168–170	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂	47.48 (47.53)	2.51 (2.56)	16.24 (16.30)
3h	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	112–114	88	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	52.09 (52.14)	3.32 (3.33)	13.47 (13.52)
3i	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	166–167	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Br	44.01 (44.06)	2.32 (2.38)	12.03 (12.09)

Table-1 (contd.)

3j	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	155-157	67	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂	53.33 (53.37)	3.92 (3.97)	16.31 (16.38)
3k	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	—	191-192	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl ₂	49.92 (49.98)	2.61 (2.69)	10.19 (10.28)
3l	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	124-126	86	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	48.68 (48.72)	2.58 (2.62)	13.31 (13.37)
3m	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	—	175-177	79	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	53.45 (53.50)	3.39 (3.46)	10.34 (10.40)
3n	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	—	168-169	79	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂ BrCl ₂	45.01 (45.08)	2.37 (2.43)	9.22 (9.28)
3o	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	135-137	81	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	54.65 (54.71)	4.01 (4.07)	13.38 (13.44)
4b	C ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	122-123	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂	55.62 (55.68)	2.83 (2.90)	13.47 (13.53)
4c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	187-189	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	59.99 (60.02)	4.25 (4.31)	8.51 (8.62)
4d	C ₆ H ₅	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	182-183	78	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂ Br ₂	49.19 (49.23)	2.53 (2.56)	7.12 (7.18)
4e	C ₆ H ₅	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	162-163	72	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ N ₅ OS ₂	66.03 (66.19)	5.02 (5.10)	17.94 (18.00)
4f	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	132-134	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	53.18 (53.21)	2.52 (2.58)	10.29 (10.35)
4g	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	146-147	84	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₇ S ₂	51.17 (51.22)	2.42 (2.49)	14.89 (14.94)
4h	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	179-180	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	58.59 (58.62)	3.72 (3.75)	10.48 (10.52)
4i	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	193-195	68	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Br ₂	45.67 (45.72)	2.19 (2.22)	8.81 (8.89)
4j	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	142-143	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂	60.12 (60.19)	4.61 (4.65)	14.90 (15.04)
4k	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	184-185	79	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl ₃	54.19 (54.26)	2.58 (2.63)	7.87 (7.92)
4l	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	158-159	76	C ₂₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂ Cl	52.17 (52.20)	2.48 (2.53)	12.61 (12.68)
4m	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	192-193	69	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	59.76 (59.80)	3.78 (3.83)	8.05 (8.05)
4n	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	167-169	88	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS ₂ Br ₂ Cl	46.43 (46.49)	2.21 (2.25)	6.72 (6.78)
4o	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	116-117	67	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl	59.72 (59.76)	4.71 (4.75)	12.69 (12.78)

Experimental

Melting points were determined in Toshniwal melting point instrument and are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesized compounds was tested by thin layer chromatography on silica gel 'G' coated plates. IR spectra

($\nu_{\max}$ in cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (δ -scale) on a Bruker DRX-300 in CDCl₃ at 200 MHz using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

Ar = C₆H₅/4-NO₂C₆H₄/4-ClC₆H₄

Ar¹/Ar² = 2-ClC₆H₄/4-NO₂C₆H₄/4-OCH₃C₆H₄/4-BrC₆H₄/
4-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄

Scheme 1

5-(Substituted phenyl)-2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1a) : A mixture of thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol) and benzoic acid (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 mL) with concentrated H₂SO₄ A.R. grade (2 mL)¹ were refluxed for about 4 h and poured into crushed ice. The solid thus obtained was separated out. It was washed with water and recrystallised from methanol to give **1a**, yield 79%, m.p. 217–221° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 223–227°) (Found : C, 54.19; H, 3.88; N, 23.61. Calcd. for C₈H₇N₃S : C, 54.21; H, 3.92; N, 23.69%); IR : 3352, 3312, (-NH₂); 3022, 1600, 1515, 760, 690 (aromatic ring);

1590, 1442, 1309, 1105, 720 (thiadiazole nucleus); ¹H NMR : δ 7.10–7.71 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.19 (2H, s, -NH₂); MS : 177 (M⁺), 100 and 77.

Other compounds **1b** and **1c** were synthesized in a similar way¹ by using 4-nitrobenzoic acid and 4-chlorobenzoic acid respectively.

(1b) : Yield 79%, m.p. 220–224° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 229–233°) (Found : C, 43.18; H, 2.65; N, 25.18. Calcd. for C₈H₆N₄O₂S : C, 43.24; H, 2.70; N, 25.22%); IR : 3354, 3314 (-NH₂); 3019, 1609, 1511, 765, 687 (aromatic ring); 1542 and 1346 (Ar-NO₂); 1587, 1437, 1312, 1104, 723 (thiadiazole nucleus); ¹H NMR : δ 7.12–7.75 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.15 (2H, s, -NH₂); MS : 218 (M⁺), 118 and 100.

(1c) : Yield 77%, m.p. 252–256° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 257–261°) (Found : C, 45.31; H, 2.78; N, 19.79. Calcd. for C₈H₆N₃SCl : C, 45.39; H, 2.83; N, 19.86%); IR : 3348, 3318 (-NH₂); 3022, 1600, 1512, 768, 690 (aromatic ring); 1594, 1441, 1305, 1102, 721 (thiadiazole nucleus); 760 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR : δ 7.12–7.69 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.18 (2H, s, -NH₂); MS : 211 (M⁺), 111 and 100.

5-(Substituted phenyl)-2-(2-substituted benzylidene amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a) : A mixture of **1a** (0.01 mol) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (35 mL) was refluxed¹⁶ on a water bath for about 5 h and cooled. The solid thus obtained was separated out, filtered and recrystallised from chloroform to afford **2a**, yield 69%, m.p. 140–141 °C (Found : C, 59.99; H, 3.28; N, 14.00. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₀N₃SCl : C, 60.10; H, 3.33; N, 14.02%); IR : 3018, 1605, 1512, 762, 693 (aromatic ring); 1625 (-N=CH); 1592, 1443, 1303, 1104, 720 (thiadiazole nucleus); 768 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR : δ 4.59 (1H, s, -N=CH), 7.15–7.73 (9H, m, Ar-H); MS : 299 (M⁺), 222, 161, 138, 111, 98 and 77.

Other compounds **2(b-o)** were synthesized similarly using various aromatic aldehydes¹⁶. Their characterization data are presented in Table 1.

[2-(Substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol}-4-oxo-thiazolidines (3a) : A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 mL) were refluxed¹⁶ on a water bath for about 6 h and cooled. The solid thus obtained was separated out which was recrystallised from methanol to afford **3a**, yield 79%, m.p. 116–118 °C (Found : C, 54.57; H, 3.19; N, 11.19. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂N₃OS₂Cl : C, 54.61; H, 3.21; N, 11.25%); IR : 3017, 1601, 1513, 761,

Table 2. Antibacterial activity data of the synthesized compounds 2(a-o), 3(a-o) and 4(a-o)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. typhimurium</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>	
	25 ppm	50 ppm	25 ppm	50 ppm	25 ppm	50 ppm
2a	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
2b	++	++	++	++	+	++
2c	+	+	-	+	+	+
2d	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++
2e	+	++	-	+	-	-
2f	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
2g	++	++	+	++	++	+++
2h	+	+	-	-	+	++
2i	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++
2j	+	++	-	+	-	++
2k	++	+++	++	++	+++	+++
2l	++	++	-	+	++	++
2m	-	+	+	++	-	+
2n	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++
2o	+	+	-	++	-	-
3a	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
3b	+	+	+	++	+	+
3c	+	++	+	+	-	+
3d	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
3e	+	++	-	-	+	+
3f	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
3g	+	+	++	++	+	+
3h	+	+	+	++	-	+
3i	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
3j	+	+	+	++	-	-
3k	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
3l	+	+	-	+	-	+
3m	+	++	+	-	+	++
3n	+++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
3o	-	+	+	+	+	++
4a	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
4b	++	++	+	++	++	++
4c	+	+	-	-	+	++
4d	+++	++++	++	+++	+++	++++
4e	+	++	+	+	+	++
4f	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
4g	+	++	-	++	-	+
4h	+	+	-	++	+	++
4i	+++	++++	++	+++	+++	++++
4j	+	++	+	++	-	+
4k	++	+++	+	++	+++	+++
4l	-	+	+	++	+	++
4m	+	+	+	++	-	+
4n	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
4o	+	++	-	+	-	+
SM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

SM = Streptomycin; inhibition diameter in mm : (-) 5-8; (+) 8-13; (++) 13-19; (+++) 19-25; (++++) 25-31.

Table 3. Antifungal activity data of the synthesized compounds 2(a-o), 3(a-o) and 4(a-o)

Compd.	<i>R. oryzae</i>			<i>C. albicans</i>			<i>A. niger</i>		
	10	50	100	10	50	100	10	50	100
2a	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
2b	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
2c	+	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	+
2d	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
2e	+	++	-	+	+	+	-	+	++
2f	++	+++	++++	+	++	+++	++	++	+++
2g	+	++	++	+	+	++	+	+	++
2h	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	++
2i	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
2j	+	+	+	-	+	++	-	-	+
2k	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
2l	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
2m	-	+	+	+	+	++	-	+	++
2n	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
2o	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
3a	+	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
3b	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	++
3c	-	+	++	-	+	+	+	+	+
3d	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
3e	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	++
3f	++	+++	++++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
3g	+	+	+	+	+	++	-	+	+
3h	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
3i	++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
3j	+	+	++	+	+	++	-	+	+
3k	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
3l	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
3m	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	++
3n	++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	++
3o	+	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++
4a	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
4b	+	+	++	+	+	++	+	+	+
4c	+	++	++	-	+	++	-	+	+
4d	++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
4e	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	++
4f	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
4g	+	+	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
4h	+	+	++	-	-	+	-	+	+
4i	+	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
4j	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++
4k	++	+++	++++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
4l	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	++
4m	+	+	++	-	-	+	+	+	++
4n	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
4o	+	+	++	-	-	+	+	+	++
GF	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++	++++

GF = Griseofulvin; inhibition diameter in mm : (-) 4-9; (+) 9-13; (++) 13-17; (+++) 17-24; (++++) 24-30.

Table 4. Diuretic activity data of some of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Normal saline loaded 5 ml/100 g b.w.	Urine out put	%Out put	Diuretic activity
2a	49.30	11.67	23.67	35.55
2b	49.96	7.84	15.69	23.65
2d	46.59	13.12	28.16	42.29
2f	49.72	11.49	23.10	34.70
2g	48.95	6.79	13.87	20.83
2i	48.42	12.96	26.74	40.16
2k	47.56	12.42	26.11	39.22
2l	46.97	7.12	15.15	22.76
2n	48.99	13.90	28.37	42.61
3a	49.99	12.46	24.92	37.43
3b	46.72	6.54	13.99	21.02
3d	46.96	13.52	28.79	43.24
3f	49.68	12.00	24.15	36.27
3g	46.72	6.54	13.99	21.02
3i	50.12	14.40	28.73	43.15
3k	48.57	12.99	26.74	40.16
3l	47.10	7.30	15.49	23.27
3n	46.12	13.79	29.90	44.30
4a	46.90	11.10	23.66	35.54
4b	49.70	7.12	14.32	21.51
4d	46.67	13.05	27.96	41.99
4f	47.56	12.42	26.11	39.22
4g	47.58	6.92	14.54	21.84
4i	47.12	13.57	28.79	43.25
4k	48.12	11.99	24.91	37.42
4l	48.95	7.42	15.15	22.76
4n	49.37	14.00	28.35	42.59
Furosemide	48.30	32.16	66.58	-
Control	48.6	7.54	15.61	-

692 (aromatic ring); 2985 (-N=CH-S); 2965 (-CH₂-S); 1715 (>C=O, cyclic); 1583, 1438, 1303, 1107, 722 (thiadiazole nucleus); 765 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR : δ 7.16–7.79 (9H, m, Ar-H), 3.60 (2H, s, -CH₂S), 3.15 (1H, s, N-CH-S); MS : 373 (M⁺), 161, 111, 101 and 77.

Other compounds **3(b-o)** were synthesized similarly from **2(b-o)** using thioglycolic acid¹⁶. Their characterization data are presented in Table 1.

[5-(Substituted arylidenes)-2-(substituted aryl)-3-{5-(substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol}]-4-oxo-thiazolidines (**4a**) : A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (35 mL) in the presence of C₂H₅ONa were refluxed¹⁶ on a water bath for about

5 h and cooled. The solid thus obtained was separated out which was recrystallised from chloroform to afford **4a**, yield 80%; m.p. 178–179 °C (Found : C, 58.03; H, 2.98; N, 8.41. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₅N₃OS₂Cl₂ : C, 58.10; H, 3.02; N, 8.46%); IR : 3012, 1615, 1504, 762, 696 (aromatic ring); 2980 (-N-CH-S); 1712 (>C=O, cyclic); 1621 (>C=CH-Ar); 1589, 1444, 1305, 1102, 719 (thiadiazole nucleus); 768 (Ar-Cl); ¹H NMR : δ 7.08–7.81 (13H, m, Ar-H), 5.26 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 3.19 (1H, s, -N-CH-S); MS : 495 (M⁺), 306, 302, 223, 161, 111, 84 and 77.

Other compounds **4(b-o)** were synthesized similarly from **3(b-o)** using various aromatic aldehydes¹⁶. Their characterization data are presented in Table 1.

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